

**Innovation Center of
Faculty of Mechanical
Engineering**

**Faculty of Mechanical
Engineering, University
of Belgrade**

**Center for Business
Trainings**

**„International Conference of Experimental and
Numerical Investigations and New Technologies“**

Sponsored by:

**MINISTRY OF EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND TECHNICAL DEVELOPMENT
OF THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA**

Programme and The Book of Abstracts

02-05 July 2019

Zlatibor, Serbia

TO GIVE OR NOT TO GIVE DIURETICS AFTER TREATMENT OF DIFFERENTIATED THYROID CANCER WITH ^{131}I , IN ORDER TO DECREASE RADIATION BURDEN TO THE PATIENTS?

V.D. Ignjatovic^{1,2}, M. Matovic^{1,2}, M. Jeremic², V. Vukomanovic^{1,2}, V.S. Ignjatovic¹, M. Popovic³

¹University of Kragujevac, Faculty of Medical Sciences, 34000, Kragujevac, Serbia

²Clinical Center Kragujevac, Department of Nuclear medicine, 34000 Kragujevac, Serbia

³Institute of oncology and radiology of Serbia, Department of Nuclear medicine, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

*Corresponding author e-mail: _vesnaivladaignjatovic@gmail.com

Abstract

After surgery, radioiodine therapy is a usual treatment in patients with differentiated thyroid carcinoma (DTC). Radioiodine (^{131}I) is mostly excreted by the kidneys; one of procedures for enhancement of ^{131}I excretion can be use of diuretics. The aim of this experimental study was to investigate the effect of hydrochlorothiazide (HCTZ) and furosemide administration on the excretion of ^{131}I compared to controls who haven't received diuretics.

Subjects and methods: Study included 90 patients with DTC, normal renal function and low ^{131}I uptake in the thyroid region. Patients were divided into three groups: HCTZ, furosemide and the control group. Patients underwent measurements of the exposition dose of ^{131}I by a survey meter with pancake probe, right after ^{131}I administration and after 72h. On the basis of the initial and the exposition dose after 72h, expressed as percentage of the initial exposition dose, and considering the administered radioactivity, the residual activity in body was calculated and expressed in megabecquerel/gigabecquerel (MBq/GBq).

Results: The residual activity in the body and the exposed dose after 72h were higher in HCTZ group (71.61 vs. 60.70MBq/GBq and 7.05% vs. 6.14%) compared to controls, but this difference was not significant. These parameters were significantly higher in furosemid group compared to HCTZ (11.24% vs. 7.05%, $p=0.031$ and 112.31 vs. 71.61MBq/GBq, $p=0.017$) and control group (112.31 vs 60.70MBq/GBq and 11.24% $p=0.025$ vs. 6.14%, $p=0.009$).

Conclusion: In this experimental study we showed that use of diuretics as additional treatment after radioiodine therapy in patients with DTC increases radioiodine retention in patient's body.

Keywords

Thyroid carcinoma, hydrochlorothiazide, furosemide, radiodine